

Extinction Coefficient of Mixtures of Copper Sulphate with Glucose, Glycerine and Sodium Formate in the Ultra-violet as Experimental Evidence in Favour of the Formation of Unstable Intermediate Compounds. Part IV.

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In a previous paper by Ghosh and Rangacharya (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 569) it has been shown that the observed exaltation in values of extinction coefficients when mercuric chloride is mixed with organic acids, can be explained quantitatively on the hypothesis that an intermediate compound is produced by the association of one molecule of mercuric chloride with one molecule of organic acid. The dissociation constants of these intermediate compounds and their extinction coefficients for several wave-lengths in the ultra-violet were calculated according to a method developed in the paper by Ghosh and Mitra (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 353).

It is well known that glucose, glycerine and formates undergo photochemical decomposition in presence of alkaline copper sulphates. The general mechanism of the photochemical decomposition is not yet definitely settled and this investigation was also undertaken with the object of finding out if the hypothesis of formation of intermediate compounds preliminary to photo-decomposition is supported by measurements of extinction coefficient of the photo-sensitive mixtures.

The experimental procedure and methods of calculation are identical with those adopted in the previous works.

Copper sulphate was employed in two forms, namely, in Benedict's solution and in Fehling's solution.

In the latter case the experimental data recorded in the tables in this paper can be quantitatively explained on the basis of—

(1) An equilibrium between copper sulphate and glucose, and copper sulphate and glycerine as reactants and the intermediate complex formed by the loose combination of one molecule of each of the reactants.

(2) The assumption of a definite value of molecular extinction coefficients for each wave-length for the intermediate complex so formed.

But in the case of copper sulphate in Benedict's solution it was observed, curiously enough, that while the first assumption was completely borne out by the experimental data at hand, the assumption of a constant value of the molecular extinction coefficient of the intermediate complex for all the wave-lengths had to be made in order to explain quantitatively the experimental results obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The Fehling's solution was made in two parts.

(A) $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (recrystallised) 6.92 gm. in 100 c. c.

(B) 13 Gm. of NaOH + 34.6 gm. of Rochelle salt in 100 c. c.

Mixture of equal volumes of (A) and (B) gave Fehling's solution.

The extinction coefficients were measured with the aid of the rotating sector-photometer of Adam Hilger in conjunction with their quartz spectrograph.

Though the photographic density of the two spectra in juxtaposition can be compared fairly accurately, still the probability of error in the value of extinction coefficients is certainly $\pm 7\%$.

The length of the tube containing the solution under investigation was 2 cm. in all the cases.

Fehling's solution of very small copper sulphate-concentration was used so that the solution showed no visible colour to the eye.

In the following tables,

$$K = \frac{\text{Conc. of intermediate compound}}{\text{Conc. of unchanged copper sulphate} \times \text{Conc. of unchanged organic molecule}}$$

x = Conc. of intermediate compound,

$E_{\text{calc.}}$ = The calculated value of the extinction coefficient of the mixture assuming a definite value of the molecular extinction coefficient (E_M^λ) for each wave-length.

TABLE I.

$M/2400\text{-CuSO}_4$ (Fehling's Sol.) and Glucose ($K=100$).

$\log I_0/I_t$ = Extinction coefficient (E)

x = Conc. of intermediate complex as calculated.

F = Fehling's solution.

(—) indicates that the extinction coefficient is negligibly small.

Wave-length ...	log I_0/I_1 for			$E_{\text{calc.}}$
	3750	3248	3036	
$M/2400$ (F), $E_{\text{obs.}}$	—	0.15	0.4	
$M/25$ -Glucose, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	—	—	—	
Mixture, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.1	0.4	0.75	0.34×10^{-3}
$E_{\text{calc.}}$	0.1	0.4	0.73	
$M/50$ -Glucose, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	—	—	—	
Mixture $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.1	0.35	0.7	0.28×10^{-3}
$E_{\text{calc.}}$	0.09	0.35	0.68	
$M/100$ -Glucose, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	—	—	—	
Mixture, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.05	0.3	0.6	0.21×10^{-3}
$E_{\text{calc.}}$	0.06	0.28	0.61	
$M/250$ -Glucose, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	—	—	—	
Mixture, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.05	0.2	0.55	0.14×10^{-3}
$E_{\text{calc.}}$	0.04	0.22	0.54	

In calculating the values of E for the various mixtures K has been assumed to be 100 in all the cases and E_M (molecular extinction coefficient of the intermediate complex) given the following values for various wave-lengths:—

Wave-length ...	3750	3248	3036
E_M ...	0.156×10^3	0.36×10^3	0.504×10^3

With $M/1200$ -copper sulphate in Fehling's solution and varying concentrations of glucose the observed values of extinctions

coefficients for mixtures could be reproduced by assuming $K=100$ and E_M given the following values for various wave-lengths.

Wave-length	... 3750	3440	3248
E_M	... 0.15×10^3	0.18×10^3	0.366×10^3

TABLE II.

M/2400-CuSO₄ (Fehling's sol.) and Glycerine (K=18).

	log I ₀ /I _t for	log I ₀ /I _t for	$\alpha_{\text{calc.}}$
Wave-length	3248	3036	
M/2400-(F), $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.15	0.4	
M/5-Glycerine, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	—	—	
Mixture, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.4	0.75	0.325×10^{-3}
$E_{\text{calc.}}$	0.39	0.75	
M/10-Glycerine, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	—	—	
Mixture, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.35	0.7	0.265×10^{-3}
$E_{\text{calc.}}$	0.35	0.69	
M/20-Glycerine, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	—	—	
Mixture, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.3	0.6	0.195×10^{-3}
$E_{\text{calc.}}$	0.31	0.61	
M/40-Glycerine, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	—	—	
Mixture, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.25	0.55	0.125×10^{-3}
$E_{\text{calc.}}$	0.25	0.54	
M/100-Glycerine, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	—	—	
Mixture, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.2	0.45	0.082×10^{-3}
$E_{\text{calc.}}$	0.19	0.47	

In obtaining the values of $E_{\text{calc.}}$ K has been assumed to be 18 in all the cases and the following values of E_M given for various wave-lengths.

Wave-length	... 3248	3036
E_M	... 39×10^3	0.56×10^3

With $M/1200$ concentration of copper sulphate in Fehling's solution and varying concentrations of glycerine extinction coefficients could be measured for higher wave-lengths and the observed values reproduced by assuming $K=18$, and E_M as given below.

Wave-length	...	3308	3164
E_M	...	0.19×10^3	0.28×10^3

The Benedict's solution consisted of: -

Anhydrous sodium carbonate	= 9 gm.
„ copper sulphate	= 1 gm.
Sodium citrate	= 17 gm.
Water	= 73 gm.
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	100 gm.

A dilute solution of copper sulphate was used.

TABLE III.

$M/16.000\text{-CuSO}_4$ (Benedict's solution) and Glucose ($K=100$).

Wave-length	log I_0/I , for			x calc.
	2507	2370	2266	
$M/16.000\text{-CuSO}_4$, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.15	0.25	0.3	
$M/25\text{-Glucose}$, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	—	—	—	
Mixture, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.4	0.5	0.55	0.050×10^{-3}
$E_{\text{calc.}}$	0.4	0.49	0.55	
$M/50\text{-Glucose}$, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	—	—	—	
Mixture, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.36	0.45	0.5	0.041×10^{-3}
$E_{\text{calc.}}$	0.36	0.45	0.5	
$M/100\text{-Glucose}$, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	—	—	—	
Mixture, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.3	0.4	0.45	0.031×10^{-3}
$E_{\text{calc.}}$	0.30	0.4	0.45	
$M/200\text{-Glucose}$, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	—	—	—	
Mixture, $E_{\text{obs.}}$	0.25	0.35	0.4	0.021×10^{-3}
$E_{\text{calc.}}$	0.24	0.3	0.4	

In obtaining the values of E_{calc} , K has been assumed to be 100 in all the cases and following constant value of E_M given.

Wave-length	...	2507	2370	2266
E_M	...	2.4×10^3	2.4×10^3	2.4×10^3

With M/8000 concentration of copper sulphate in Benedict's solution and varying concentrations of glucose extinction coefficients could be measured for higher wave-lengths and the observed values reproduced by assuming $K=100$ and E_M as given below.

Wave-length	...	2270	2507	2870
E_M	...	2.4×10^3	2.4×10^3	2.4×10^3

TABLE IV.

M/16000-CuSO₄ (Benedict's solution) and Sodium Formate (K=10).

Wave-length	log I ₀ /I, for				x calc.
	2770	2667	2400	2370	
M/16000-CuSO ₄ , E_{obs} .	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	
M/5-Sodium formate, E_{obs} .	—	—	0.15	0.2	
Mixture, E_{obs} .	0.3	0.35	0.55	0.65	0.041×10^{-3}
E_{calc} .	0.3	0.35	0.55	0.65	
M/10-Sodium formate, E_{obs} .	—	—	0.1	0.15	
Mixture, E_{obs} .	0.25	0.3	0.45	0.55	0.031×10^{-3}
E_{calc} .	0.25	0.30	0.44	0.55	
M/20-Sodium formate, E_{obs} .	—	—	0.05	0.1	
Mixture, E_{obs} .	0.2	0.25	0.35	0.45	0.021×10^{-3}
E_{calc} .	0.2	0.25	0.34	0.44	
M/50-Sodium formate, E_{obs} .	—	—	—	0.05	
Mixture, E_{obs} .	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.35	0.01×10^{-3}
E_{calc} .	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.35	

In obtaining the values of E_{calc} , K has been assumed to be 10 in all the cases and the following constant values of E_M given.

Wave-length	...	2770	2667	2400	2370
E_M	...	2.39×10^3	2.39×10^3	2.39×10^3	2.39×10^3

With $M/8000$ -concentration of copper sulphate in the Benedict's solution and varying concentrations of sodium formate extinction coefficients for mixtures could be measured and the observed values reproduced by assuming $K=10$ and $E_M = 2.4 \times 10^3$ for all wave-lengths.

Wave-length	...	2667	2469	2400	2370
E_M	...	2.4×10^3	2.4×10^3	2.4×10^3	2.4×10^3

It will be seen that the dissociation constant of the complex intermediate compound between glucose and complex copper salt is 100 both when Fehling's solution and Benedict's solution are used. The value of K diminishes from 100 in the case of glucose complex, to 18 for the glycerine complex and to 10 for the sodium formate complex.

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